

THE DEVELOPMENT OF WESTERN MEDICINE IN VIETNAM DURING THE FRENCH COLONIAL PERIOD: POLICIES AND TRAINING ACTIVITIES FOR DOCTORS AND MEDICAL STAFF (1892-1945)

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Abstract

When the French invaded Vietnam, they disrupted the traditional Eastern medical system to establish a Western medical system. Initially, they set up a network of hospitals and clinics and brought doctors and medical staff from France to work. As the French began to exploit the colonies in Indochina, the demand for medical personnel increased, and the team from the metropole could not meet the needs of the healthcare system. In 1902, the French authorities officially implemented a policy of Western medical training in Vietnam by establishing the Hanoi Medical School. Over more than 40 years of existence and development, besides Hanoi Medical School, the French also opened the Native Practical Medical School in Southern Vietnam. The implementation of these policies and the activities of Western medical training underwent many changes and ups and downs but yielded positive results. The policies and activities of Western medical training marked a fundamental transformation of Vietnam's healthcare system, bringing it closer to global medical achievements. Though a product of colonialism and serving primarily the colonial elite, the Western medical training activities in Vietnam during the French colonial period still offer valuable lessons for developing Vietnam's healthcare today.

Keywords: doctors, medical staff, training activities, Western medicine

1. INTRODUCTION

Vietnam has long been a land of traditional Eastern medicine, also known as "Dong Y". For centuries, the feudal state of Vietnam had only one institution responsible for the health of the king and the royal family within the palace, called the Imperial Medical Institute. Recruitment for this institution was selective, choosing from among the few individuals "skilled in medicine" within the populace (Le Tran Duc, 1995). The feudal state of Vietnam never organized or trained a workforce of doctors and medical staff. In the mid-19th century, when the French invaded and established a colonial regime in Vietnam, Western medicine was introduced and developed. Starting with the establishment of hospitals to treat military personnel during the invasion wars in Saigon and Hanoi, the colonial government set up a Western medical system in Vietnam with medical facilities (including military medical facilities and Catholic medical facilities), epidemic prevention and clean water facilities, and pharmaceutical companies in Saigon, Hanoi, and several provinces (Bui Thi Ha, 2024). To meet the growing needs of the Western medical system, from the early 20th century, the French began to implement a policy of training doctors and medical staff in Vietnam. How did this medical training unfold in Vietnam? What impact did it have on the development of Western medicine in Vietnam? These questions remain largely unexamined by scholars. A comprehensive review of the French colonial medical training activities in Vietnam has significant scientific value; it will help clarify the history of Vietnamese medicine and the foundations and development path of the Western medical system in Vietnam. This article presents the development of the training activities for doctors and medical staff by the French colonial government as they established the Western medical system in Vietnam during the first half of the 20th century.

2. DOCUMENTS AND RESEARCH METHODS

To date, publications on Western medicine in Vietnam remain quite sparse. Since the establishment of the first hospitals, which laid the foundation for Western medicine in Vietnam, no comprehensive publication has evaluated the overall formation and development of the healthcare system in general, and the training of doctors and medical staff in particular. The most notable recent publication is "Western Medicine in Northern Vietnam 1873-1945," which discusses the historical context and the healthcare network established by the French colonial government in Northern Vietnam from 1873 to 1945 (Bui Thi Ha, 2024). Publications directly related to the research topic are mainly short articles on some individual achievements of medical training institutions (Le Xuan Phan, 2021a, 2021b; Hanoi Medical University, 2002). Besides these direct publications, healthcare activities in Vietnam during the French colonial period are also indirectly mentioned in some studies on Vietnamese society, which include issues related to healthcare activities; however, these publications are few, and the information on healthcare activities is introduced only briefly (Charles Maybon, 2006; Dao Thi Dien, 2010).

To evaluate the policy of training doctors and medical staff in Vietnam during the French colonial period, this study relies on archival documents, including decrees, ordinances, and reports from the colonial government directly related to the policy of developing medical schools and training medical staff. These documents were issued by the French President and the Governor-General of Indochina (Gouverneur général de l'Indochine - GGI), and published in the Official Gazette of French Indochina (Journal officiel de l'Indochine française - JOIF) from 1902 to 1945. There are over 20 documents, including decrees, ordinances, and decisions related to the establishment of medical train-

ing institutions, the organization, activities, and training policies at medical schools, and the consolidation and improvement of medical schools. These documents are currently archived at the National Archives Center I in Vietnam.

Regarding research methods, this article uses the historical educational research method with a specialized approach. Data related to the establishment, organizational activities, training policies, and training outcomes of the French colonial government's medical training in Vietnam are selectively chosen to represent typical cases, presented systematically, and linked to the events that occurred. By combining descriptions of selected typical events, the article strives to capture and highlight the process of establishing and implementing medical training, observing the outcomes of these medical training events. It aims to convey the historical events and distill historical rules in medical training in Vietnam during the French colonial period.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The establishment of the first Western medical training institutions in Vietnam (1902-1906)

From the moment the French colonial government began occupying Southern Vietnam, they brought in military doctors and established small medical stations to care for patients and the wounded. In 1861, a hospital named *Hôpital Militaire*, also known as *Don Dat Hospital*, was established in Saigon. Following this, in 1862, the French established a second hospital in Saigon named *Cho Quan Hospital* (*Hôpital de Cho Quan*), which treated venereal disease patients and sick prisoners. These were the first Western medical facilities in Vietnam. By the 1870s, as the French advanced into Northern Vietnam, they organized military medical facilities under the French Naval Health Service in Hanoi. In 1873, the French successively built hospitals in Hanoi, Haiphong, and Lang Thuong (now Bac Giang) (Bui Thi Ha, 2024). By the 1890s, the network of Western medical facilities in Vietnam was relatively widespread, but there were no institutions for training medical personnel. In 1901, the French authorities opened the first male nursing class at Cho Quan Hospital, marking the first Western medical training program in Vietnam. However, up to this point, the French government had not yet established specific policies for training medical staff.

In 1897, the French appointed Paul Doumer, a civilian politician, as the Governor-General of Indochina to commence economic exploitation of the colony. Upon his arrival in Vietnam, Paul Doumer implemented numerous economic development policies such as mining, rubber plantation development, rice cultivation, expanding transportation networks, and building commercial ports in Saigon and Haiphong. The primary objective of the colonial government was to exploit the controlled territory, which necessitated attention to human resources to realize that goal. This was the initial aim of all plans executed by the French in Vietnam. They determined that "the main effort must be to prevent the key factors that reduce the population, such as

diseases and epidemics, whose impact not only increases mortality rates but also reduces labor efficiency. Healthcare plays an important role in the exploitation of the colony" (Gastaldy, 1931). In this context, the authorities mobilized and encouraged doctors from France to work in Vietnam, but the results were minimal; the shortage of doctors and medical staff was a serious problem in Indochina in general, and in Vietnam in particular.

To meet the demands of developing and maintaining the hospital system and maternity homes in Hanoi, Saigon, and the provinces, in January 1902, the Governor-General of Indochina (GGI) issued a decree establishing the Hanoi Medical School, placing it under the GGI's control (GGI, 1902). According to this decree, the Hanoi Medical School was tasked with training Asian doctors capable of undertaking medical work in Indochina alongside and under the direction of French doctors; participating in scientific research and providing medical treatment to Europeans and indigenous people in Indochina. The school's activities included teaching and research. Teaching activities for Asian students comprised theoretical lectures and practical training, with internships conducted at a hospital in Hanoi affiliated with the school. Research activities were for resident scientists and some seconded scientists, with specialized laboratories serving research purposes. The school's teaching staff included professors appointed from among civilian doctors in the home country or Indochina, or military doctors in Indochina; lecturers were selected from civilian doctors in the colony, military doctors, and pharmacists residing in Hanoi and working in military hospitals. The school also had policies for those without medical degrees but with knowledge in certain scientific fields, allowing them to be recruited and appointed as professors or lecturers (GGI, 1902).

Although the decree to establish the Hanoi Medical School was issued in early January 1902, the school could not immediately become operational. In February 1902, the GGI issued another decree establishing a council to complete the Hanoi Medical School, tasked with addressing operational and organizational issues, and proposing measures to ensure the school's functionality. The council was also responsible for budgeting, purchasing and installing equipment, setting the number and methods of student recruitment, study regimes, and student classification after completing their courses (GGI, 1902a).

With the council's preparations, in July 1902, the GGI issued a decree outlining the curriculum and admission requirements for the Hanoi Medical School. This decree set a training duration of 3.5 years. For admissions, the school accepted and provided scholarships to indigenous students aged 15 to 20, who were French citizens or under French protection, proficient in French, and had basic elementary education knowledge. The school's curriculum included a preparatory stage and a main course stage. The preparatory stage lasted one year with subjects like anatomy and physiology concepts, zoology, chemistry and physics, botany, arithmetic and geometry, French, geography, and history. After completing the preparatory course,

students began the main course lasting three years. The first year included subjects like theoretical anatomy, dissection, physiology, surgical histology, clinical medicine, zoology, botany, chemistry, French, and history. The second year included subjects like dissection, theoretical anatomy, general pathology, internal and external pathology, pathological anatomy, pharmacology, clinical medicine, and surgery, physiology, physics, chemistry, geology, and astronomy. The third year included subjects like regional anatomy, bacteriology, embryology, hygiene, therapeutics, forensic medicine, dermatology, ophthalmic clinic, dental clinic, and obstetrics clinic. At the end of the three years, students took a comprehensive exam in all subjects studied. Those who passed were awarded a medical degree. Graduates of the Hanoi Medical School could be appointed to certain official positions and participate in competitive exams for local hospital positions (GGI, 1992b).

After establishing the Hanoi Medical School, the French continued to set up the Indigenous Medical Practice School in Southern Vietnam. In August 1903, the GGI issued a decree establishing the Indigenous Medical Practice School in Southern Vietnam with the aim of training Vietnamese nurses and midwives (GGI, 1903). The nursing department was located at Cho Quan Hospital, headed by the hospital's director. Students were selected through a recruitment process from the provinces, with each province allowed to select no more than two students per year. The nurse training lasted two years. The theoretical subjects included general concepts of symptomatology and pathology, anatomy concepts, malaria, plague, and infectious diseases, cholera, smallpox, beriberi, measles, gonorrhoea, orchitis, syphilis, dermatology, leprosy, scabies, sores, drowning rescue techniques, hemorrhage, fractures, sprains, minor surgery. Practical training included vaccination techniques, bandaging, pharmacology concepts. Students alternated between theoretical and practical training, with two months of theory followed by two months of practice. After each practical phase, students underwent an exam; those who passed were awarded a vaccination nurse certificate and appointed as vaccination staff. Those who failed were dismissed. The midwifery department admitted up to 12 students per course twice a year. The curriculum included basic concepts from a textbook by Dr. Angier and practical skills taught at Cho Lon Maternity Hospital. Graduates were appointed as nurse-midwives in local health stations or maternity homes established by local authorities (GGI, 1903).

After two years, Western medical training activities were not as expected. The number of students was very low, and recruitment was difficult due to the low educational level of Vietnamese students; hiring lecturers was also challenging as most doctors were reluctant to work in the colonies. In response to this situation, in 1904, the GGI decided to restructure the Hanoi Medical School. The Governor-General of Indochina issued a decree defining the functions, administration, curriculum, salaries, students, and policies on study, examinations, and degrees of the Hanoi Medical School. According to this decree, the Hanoi Medical School would

be renamed the Indochina Medical School, with the function of training Asian doctors under French management to ensure local medical work and contribute to sanitation and disease prevention throughout Indochina; training indigenous midwives and veterinarians (GGI, 1904).

The school's administration was appointed by the GGI, with European personnel holding managerial positions. Salaries and allowances were double those in the home country. Students were divided into three departments: Medicine, Midwifery, and Veterinary Medicine. Medical students received full scholarships (covering food, accommodation, and monthly stipends); after graduation, they were allowed to practice under current laws in Indochina. Midwifery students also received scholarships and stipends from local government budgets. Veterinary Medicine students received scholarships and living allowances; graduates were appointed as local veterinarians (GGI, 1904).

The medical curriculum lasted four years. The first year included theoretical anatomy and physiology, clinical and surgical practice, and dissection. The second year included theoretical anatomy and physiology, internal and external pathology, clinical medicine and surgery, pharmacology, and dissection. The third year included theoretical anatomy and physiology, internal and external pathology, clinical medicine and surgery, hygiene, therapeutics, and pharmacology concepts, obstetrics, and dissection. In the fourth year, students were sent to hospitals, health stations, leprosy camps, or other health facilities designated by the GGI, as recommended by the Medical School Principal and approved by the relevant units. The Midwifery program lasted two years. In the first year, students learned about the structure of reproductive organs, physiology concepts, hygiene, practical training in obstetrics, vaccination concepts, and vaccination practice. In the second year, students practiced normal delivery, postnatal care concepts, hygiene for pregnant and postpartum women, infant hygiene, and practical training in obstetrics. The Veterinary Medicine program lasted two years. The first year included subjects like anatomy, physiology, pharmacology, hygiene, and horse characteristics. The second year included subjects like pathology, clinical studies, surgical techniques, infectious diseases, and veterinary hygiene; horse shoeing techniques, and livestock management. At the end of the course, students who passed the exams were awarded diplomas. The medical, midwifery, and veterinary diplomas were written in Latin and Chinese, signed by the GGI, or the Director of the Health Department and the Medical School Principal (GGI, 1904).

3.2. Medical training at The Indochina University 1906-1945

In 1906, the French colonial authorities established the Council for the Improvement of Indigenous Education and officially began the first educational reform in Indochina. The French government established the Indochina University, which comprised five member schools: the School of Law and Administration, the School of Sciences, the Medical School, the School of Civil Engineering, and the School of Literature. From this point, the Indochina Medical School became a

member of the Indochina University. The Medical School was the only operational school within the Indochina University at that time (Tran Thi Phuong Hoa, 2012).

In 1909, the Medical School underwent restructuring in terms of both management and curriculum. The management personnel included professors in charge of teaching (professors, practicing doctors, and lecturers); the Indigenous Midwifery Department was assigned to a French midwife with a university degree; the position of the Dean was given to one of the professors or doctors from the Department of Health. The Dean directed the academic programs with the assistance of the Council for Improvement. This Council was responsible for researching issues related to the operation and development of the affiliated units. The Council had to be consulted on budget preparation, curriculum development, admission requirements, and the selection of lecturers. The Council's members included the Resident Superior of Tonkin, the Director of the Department of Health, the provincial mandarins, the Dean of the Medical School, the Director of the Indigenous Hospital, one lecturer, and one doctor from the Department of Health (GGI, 1909).

Regarding training, the Medical School restructured its student body, curriculum, and post-graduation work policies. Besides boarding students admitted through the selection process, free students were also accepted as day students without having to pay tuition fees. The number of scholarship recipients was capped at six per year, including four Vietnamese, one Laotian, and one Cambodian. Upon admission, students had to commit to working as indigenous doctors for at least ten years after graduation. Medical students were also exempted from the personal tax and military service.

The medical program lasted four years. The first year included courses in basic anatomy, the application of physical and natural sciences in medicine, and introductory hospital practice. The second year covered anatomy and physiology, dissection, internal and external pathology, hospital practice, and clinical lessons. The third year included advanced dissection and anatomy, internal and external pathology, childbirth practice, and clinical lessons. The fourth year focused on internal and external pathology, advanced childbirth

practice, clinical lessons, pharmacology, therapeutics, and hygiene. Graduation exams consisted of both theoretical and practical sections, including internal medicine, surgical treatment, obstetrics, pathology, childbirth practice, and drug preparation. Graduates received a diploma and were appointed as third-class indigenous doctors as per GGI regulations.

The Midwifery Department admitted both free students and scholarship recipients. The maximum number of scholarships per year was five. The program lasted two years. The first year included courses in the anatomy and physiology of reproductive organs, an overview of pregnancy and childbirth, breastfeeding methods, infant hygiene, and vaccination. The second year included practical midwifery, physiology during pregnancy and postpartum, hygiene for pregnant women and infants, and practical lessons in obstetrics and vaccination. Graduates who passed the final exams received a diploma in Midwifery and were appointed as third-class midwives in health stations or hospitals (GGI, 1909).

In 1913, the Medical School's curriculum was further improved. Specific regulations on functions, duties, management policies, personnel, and salary levels were established. The school was officially named the Indochina Medical School, part of the Indochina University, with the function of training indigenous doctors under the guidance of French physicians, ensuring indigenous medical work, and contributing to hygiene measures across Indochina; training indigenous midwives; inspecting health institutions, and submitting evaluation reports to the GGI. The staff included professors, hospital directors, and lecturers appointed by the GGI. The Midwifery Department had one obstetrics lecturer and one French midwife appointed by the GGI.

The Indochina Medical School admitted students under 25 years old who graduated from Franco-Vietnamese secondary schools and had good health and moral character. All medical students received full boarding scholarships, free meals and accommodation, monthly stipends, and exemptions from personal tax and military service. The duration of the medical program remained four years, and the midwifery program was two years, with many improvements (GGI, 1913).

Table 1

Training Duration and Curriculum of the Indochina Medical School in 1913 (GGI, 1913)

No	Training Department	Year	Curriculum
1	Medical	1	Descriptive anatomy; dissection; practical symptomatology; minor surgery; hospital practice
		2	Descriptive anatomy; dissection; physiology; internal pathology; external pathology; symptomatology; hygiene; minor surgery; hospital practice
		3	Topographic anatomy; internal pathology; external pathology; obstetrics; hygiene; pharmacology; clinical medicine; hospital practice
		4	Internal pathology; external pathology; hybrid surgery; obstetrics; hygiene; pharmacology; practical concepts in dentistry; clinical medicine; clinical surgery; hospital practice
2	Midwifery	1	Overview of anatomy and physiology; basics of pregnancy and postpartum; hospital practice
		2	Practical midwifery; pathology during pregnancy and postpartum; hygiene for pregnant women and postpartum; hygiene for infants; vaccination; hospital practice

A significant change in Western medical training in Vietnam occurred in 1918 when the colonial government issued the general regulations on higher education in Indochina (*Reblement général de l'Enseignement supérieur en Indochine*). To reform higher education, the colonial authorities established the Steering Committee "to centralize the administrative work of all schools under the University of Indochina, including establishment, organizational work regimes, drafting, and issuing programs... For medical and pharmaceutical training, the Indochina Medical School was tasked with training doctors and assistant pharmacists for the Indochina Health Department and indigenous midwives. The school was organized into three departments: the

Medical Department, the Pharmaceutical Department, and the Midwifery Department (GGI, 1918).

In the Medical Department, teaching was conducted by professors and lecturers appointed by GGI at the suggestion of the head of the higher education Steering Committee. These appointments were selected from among civilian doctors, pharmacists, or doctors of the colonial expeditionary force or the Health Department based on the recommendations of the relevant unit heads. Besides professors and doctors, the Medical Department also had an obstetrics lecturer and a qualified French midwife appointed by GGI. Additionally, the Medical Department included a hospital interpreter appointed by the principal, who was responsible for basic French classes for students (GGI, 1918).

Table 2

Duration and Curriculum of the Medical Department, Indochina Medical School 1918 (GGI, 1918)

First Year	Preliminary instruction in physical sciences, chemistry, and natural sciences according to the metropolitan curriculum; Descriptive anatomy (osteology, arthrology, myology, angiology); Dissection; Minor surgery; Bandaging practice; Hospital practice
Second Year	Descriptive anatomy (splanchnology, neurology, sensory organs); Dissection; Physiology; Internal pathology; External pathology; Symptomatology; Hygiene; Minor surgery; Hospital practice
Third Year	Topographic anatomy; Internal pathology; External pathology; Obstetrics; Hygiene (sanitary measures and prevention of infectious diseases); Pharmacology; Practical exercises; Dosage studies; Clinical medicine; Clinical surgery; Clinical obstetrics; Hospital practice
Fourth Year	Internal pathology; External pathology; Obstetrics; Hygiene; Sanitary measures and prevention of infectious diseases; Forensic medicine; Pharmacology; Practical exercises; Dosage studies; Practical concepts in dentistry; Clinical medicine; Clinical surgery; Clinical obstetrics; Clinical dentistry; Clinical therapeutics; Hospital practice

The Pharmaceutical Department was a new unit in the training program of the Indochina Medical School. Teaching was conducted by military or civilian pharmacists recruited as lecturers. The training duration was three years. The curriculum included preliminary and main courses. Preliminary courses comprised physical, chemical, and natural sciences (shared with the Medical Department). Main courses included general and physical chemistry, inorganic chemistry, chemical nomenclature, nonmetals, metals, organic chemistry, biochemistry, biological analysis, general physics, practical physics, natural history, general botany, medical zoology, specialized botany, pharmacology (tobacco), veterinary science, chemical pharmacology, hygiene, hydrology, toxicology. Practical exercises in pharmacology, chemistry, and analytical chemistry were conducted in the mornings at the Indigenous Protection Hospital and the Medical Department Laboratory. Graduates of the Pharmaceutical Department were appointed by GGI as doctors or intern assistant pharmacists at hospitals (GGI, 1918).

The Midwifery Department admitted female students aged 17 and above, of native origin, with clear backgrounds, good morals, and proficient French. Midwifery students received free boarding and allowances funded by the school's budget. Those with families living in Hanoi were allowed to reside outside but did not receive any allowances. The program lasted two years. The first year included subjects such as anatomy and physiology, the female reproductive system, general knowledge of pregnancy and childbirth, and hospital

practice. The second year included practical midwifery, pathology of pregnancy and postpartum, infant hygiene, vaccination, and hospital practice. Graduates were awarded diplomas signed by the Resident Superior of Tonkin, the Chief Inspector of Health Services in Indochina, and the Principal of the Medical and Pharmaceutical School (GGI, 1918).

In 1923, the President of the French Republic (*Président de la République Française - PRF*) decided to establish the Indochina School of Medicine and Pharmacy. According to the presidential decree, the Indochina Medical School was upgraded to the Indochina School of Medicine and Pharmacy (*Ecole de Médecine et de Pharmacie en plein exercice*), continuing to train physicians, pharmacists, and indigenous assistants in the health sector and midwives under GGI's conditions. The organization of the Indochina School of Medicine and Pharmacy included a Principal appointed by GGI. Teaching staff consisted of tenured professors, lecturers, and research team leaders. The curriculum included subjects such as anatomy, physiology, pathology, histology, and pathological anatomy, hygiene, anatomical medicine, therapeutics, medical physics and chemistry, gynecology, bacteriology. Clinical subjects included clinical surgery, clinical medicine, pediatrics (PRF, 1923).

The transition of the Indochina Medical School to a fully-fledged institution was a necessary completion of higher education organization in Indochina. With the organization of the Indochina School of Medicine and

Pharmacy, the Western medical training model in Vietnam became similar to that of the metropolis, with the addition of departments for Indochinese physicians and pharmacists. These new regulations led to the establishment of departments such as Histology, Pathological Anatomy, Practical Surgery, Bacteriology, Parasitology, Physiology, and Medical Chemistry – previously non-existent. The curriculum was enhanced with more integrated practical training in these departments, bringing the quality of Indochinese physicians closer to that of metropolitan doctors. Students could transfer to schools in the metropolis or Algeria for personal or other reasons, especially those with colonial faculties, and students from tropical medicine faculties in France could also transfer to the Indochina school (Le Xuan Phan, 2021a).

3.3. Some results of Western medical education by the colonial government

Western medical education in Vietnam was implemented quite early by the French colonial authorities and had the longest continuous operation among the colleges and universities established by the French in Indochina before 1945. From 1907 to 1930, despite the difficult admissions conditions at the University of Indochina, where many schools faced interruptions due to lack of enrollment, the medical school was the only institution that maintained continuous operation and graduated students annually. According to preliminary statistics, from 1907 to 1930, a total of 285 doctors, pharmacists, and midwives graduated. Although this number is relatively small by today's standards, it significantly contributed to the healthcare workforce in Vietnam during the colonial period. Diagram 1 below provides a preliminary statistical overview of the number of medical school graduates in Vietnam from 1907 to 1930 (Hoang Hang, 2016).

Chart 1: Number of Graduates from Hanoi Medical School 1907-1930

According to Nguyen Phuong Hoa (2012), the years 1932-1935 marked a positive development in medical education in Vietnam. The École de Médecine et de Pharmacie and the Law School were the two strongest institutions of the University of Indochina, with only the École de Médecine et de Pharmacie consistently producing graduates. The departments of General Medicine and Pharmacy developed into full-fledged faculties training doctors and pharmacists. These faculties were recognized as affiliates of the

Paris Medical Institute. Over five years (1939-1944), enrollment doubled, reaching over 200 students in the 1944-1945 academic year. From 1930 to 1945, the Hanoi Medical School experienced its most glorious period. During this time, the school awarded medical doctorates equivalent to those in France and granted state pharmacist degrees (Le Van Phan, 2021a). The scale of student enrollment at the Hanoi Medical School from 1930-1945 is illustrated in Chart 2 below.

Chart 2: Student Enrollment at Hanoi Medical University 1930-1944

4. Conclusion

Western medical education was an entirely new activity in Vietnam. By establishing medical schools and setting up training programs, the French colonial authorities not only created a Western medical system in Vietnam that included both healthcare services and medical training but also laid the foundation for a health science discipline for the colonial population. Despite the fact that the benefits of this system primarily served the ruling class and most of the general population did not reap its rewards, the introduction of Western medicine marked a fundamental shift in Vietnam's healthcare system. This significant transformation in the history of Vietnamese healthcare also helped lay the groundwork for the country's medical sector in subsequent periods. Notably, Western medical training institutions produced excellent doctors who later became the backbone of the healthcare system of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam and then the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, helping integrate Vietnamese healthcare with global medical achievements. Many doctors trained under the French colonial regime became world-renowned physicians, such as Dr. Ton That Tung. A student at the medical school from 1935 to 1939, Dr. Tung became one of the leading liver surgeons of the 20th century alongside figures like Hugo Rex, James Cantlie, Jean-Louis Lortat-Jacob, Jacques Hepp, Claude Couinaud, Henri Bismuth, Thomas Starzl, and Roy Calne. His method of planned liver resection was a groundbreaking contribution to global medical achievements in the 20th century, and it was also his graduation thesis at the Hanoi Medical School in 1939 (Thomas and Daniel, 2020).

To this day, over 100 years later, the achievements of Western medical training in Vietnam during the colonial era still offer lessons for Vietnamese medical educators. Today, it is difficult to explain why, despite limited and outdated facilities and a weak teaching

staff, the training results were outstanding. Given the challenging living conditions in Indochina at that time, most skilled doctors preferred to stay in Paris rather than work in the colonies. Even military physicians could be appointed as professors in colonial medical schools, yet many students excelled, with numerous doctoral theses from the *École de Médecine et de Pharmacie* presented at Paris Medical Conferences, a prestigious medical forum in France at the time.

The French colonial regime brought with it a deeply ingrained political agenda. The ruling class maintained a strict distinction between "metropolitan" and "native" people, asserting French superiority and civilization over Vietnam. This prejudiced and discriminatory view was evident in medical education. However, most medical students overcame these obstacles and became exceptional doctors for Vietnam. This phenomenon requires analysis and research to inform contemporary medical education in Vietnam.

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